

Study on Marketing of Flower (Rose and Marigold) in Prayagraj District of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:- The aesthetic value of flowers and ornamental plants, their use in social events, overall satisfaction in working with them and high income generating power are attracting modern entrepreneurs to invest money in the floriculture industry. The demand for flowers and ornamental plants for different needs like religious, official ceremonies, parties, house decoration, weddings, funerals, etc, is on the rise. This demand for fresh flowers and plants is increasing world-wide over the coming years. The recent liberalization policy of the Government of India has given Phillip to commercialized agriculture particularly horticultural crops. Rose and marigold flowers play a prominent role among cut-flowers. The government of India has also identified floriculture as a suitable area with vast potential for export. Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*, *Tagetes patula*) flower cultivation is getting increasingly popular among farmers. Marigold, belonging to family Asteraceae, is an important ornamental herb grown for its highly decorative and long lasting flowers. I work on Prayagraj District of Uttar Pradesh. In Prayagraj district the main work of my project is to visit the missing Market and meet to the farmers to address the farmers about the economic benefit of adopting floriculture and understand the value chain supply of marketing of rose and marigold.. A Sample of 120 respondents was drawn by proportional to area under Prayagraj . The farmers were divided into marginal, small, semi-medium, medium, large with the cumulative total method. The sample included 15 marginal, 38 small, 25 Semi medium 30 medium 12 large respondents. . It is revealed that marketing of rose and marigold is working over three marketing channel, out of which the majorly used channel is channel 3.

Keywords:- Rose, Marigold, Marketing Channel, Market Margin, Marketing Cost, Market Efficiency, Price Spread and Producer Share in Consumer Rupee.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rose and marigold flowers play a prominent role among cut-flowers. The government of India has also identified floriculture as a suitable area with vast potential for export. Nowadays, water scarcity is a major issue. In spite of these problems, the rose has to be cultivated

according to the patterns. A suitable climatic condition is also an issue. Apart from this, there is no alternative flower that can be used in the place of rose and marigold flower.

Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*, *Tagetes patula*) flower cultivation is getting increasingly popular among farmers. Marigold, belonging to family Asteraceae, is an important ornamental herb grown for its highly decorative and long lasting flowers. Marigold is a very important flowering plant useful for cut flowers, garlands, garden disc play, loose flowers and perfume industries. Marigold is one such potential flower crops for natural colour extraction. Marigold is not only grown as ornamental cut flowers and landscape plant but also as a source of ceremonies like wedding, birthday, and marriage day greetings, religious offerings and sometimes in social, political, and historical occasions. The growing of this beautiful flower in India developed with the distillation of roses and marigold as mentioned in the Ayurveda. Throughout the history no flower has been as loved, or renowned as the rose and marigold . Rose and marigold is older than the human hands that first cared for it, drew pictures of it, and celebrated rose and marigold in music and lore. Fossils have also been found in Germany and in Yugoslavia. Roses grow wild as far north as Norway and Alaska and as far south as Mexico and North Africa, but no wild roses have ever been found to grow below the equator. Marigolds are native to subtropical America and have been cultivated in Mexico for over 2,000 years. Marigold cultivars are usually sold as part of a series with similar growth characteristics and a wide range of colours.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ Selection of District:

There are 75 District and 18 division in Uttar Pradesh state. Out of these Prayagraj district of Uttar Pradesh was selected purposively and this there are four sub-division (Prayagraj, Pratapgarh, Prayagraj and Fatehpur) for the present study on the basis of maximum area under flower cultivation.

➤ Selection of Block:

There are 23 block in the district. Out of these Chaka was selected purposively for the study.

➤ *Selection of Village:*

There are total 137 village in Chaka block obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages were arranged in order on the basis of area of cultivation. Thus out of total villages 5% villages were selected randomly for the present study.

➤ *Selection of Respondents:*

From the selected village list of all the rose and marigold cultivator was obtained from the block development office in each selected village. Ascending order on the basis of size of their land holding for the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 120 farmers was randomly selected from each village and then the selected farmers was classified into five sizes of groups. Distribution of selected rose and marigold.

Table 1 Distribution of Selected Rose and Marigold Grower in Chaka block:

Sr. No.	Size Group	Total No. of Growers	No. of Selected Grower
1.	Marginal	75	15
2.	Small farmers	75	38
3.	Semi-Medium	85	25
4.	Medium farmers	85	30
5.	Large farmers	150	12
Total		520	120

➤ *Selection of Market:*

Two types of market was selected purposively for the present study.

Primary Market- The primary market (Naini Phool Mandi etc) was selected purposively. Secondary market- Regulated market was selected purposively.

➤ *Analytical Tools:*

• *Standard Deviation:*

A standard deviation is a measure how dispersed the data is in relation to the mean. Low standard deviation means data are classified around the mean, and high standard deviation indicates data are more spread out. To calculate the standard deviation, use the following formula

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

Where,

σ = population standard deviation.

N = the size of the population.

x_i = each value from the population.

μ = the population mean.

➤ *Mean Median Mode:*

• *Mean:*

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

• *Median:*

$$\text{Med}(X) = \begin{cases} X[\frac{n+1}{2}] & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{X[\frac{n}{2}] + X[\frac{n}{2}+1]}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Where,

X = ordered list of values in data set.

n = number of values in data set

• *Mode:*

$$\text{Mode} = L + h \frac{(f_m - f_1)}{(f_m - f_1) + (f_m - f_2)}$$

Where,

L is the lower limit of the modal class

H is the size of the class interval

f_m is the frequency of the modal class

f_1 is the frequency of the class preceding the modal class

f_2 is the frequency of the class succeeding the modal class

• *Market Margin:*

Market margin = Product Price – Raw material

• *Market Cost:*

$$\text{Marketing cost (MC)} = \frac{\Delta TC}{\Delta Q}$$

Where,
 Δ = Change
 TC = Total Cost
 Q = Quantity

• *Marketing Efficiency:*

$$ME = \frac{\text{Output produce}}{\text{Input used}}$$

• *Price Spread:*

$$\text{Price spread} = \frac{(\text{Consumer price} - \text{Net Price of Producer}) \times 100}{\text{Consumer price}}$$

• *Producer’s Share in Consumer Rupee:*

$$F_s = \frac{F_p \times 100}{C_p}$$

Where,

- ✓ F_s = farmer’s share in consumer rupee (percentage)
- ✓ F_p = farmer’s net selling price
- ✓ C_p = consumer’s price

• *Garrett Ranking*

$$\text{Percent position} = \frac{100(R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = rank given for i^{th} factor by j^{th} individual
 N_j = number of factors ranked by j^{th} individual

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 Distribution of Respondent based on their Preference on Marketing Channel

Sr. No.	Channel Type	No of respondent	Percentage
1	Channel – I	20	16.67%
2	Channel – II	35	29.16%
3	Channel -III	65	54.17%
Total		120	100%

➤ *Table 2:*

Through these marketing channel, Rose and Marigold move from the actual producer to the consumers. The marketing channel- III involves highest number of intermediaries. Marketing Channel- II involves one intermediaries whereas the marketing channel- I involves no intermediary. During the case study in Prayagraj district in Uttar Pradesh, it has been found that maximum quantity of rose and marigold moves through the marketing channels - III that is “Producer – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer.

➤ *Table 3:*

Market margin, Marketing cost, Marketing efficiency, Price spread and Producer’s Share in Consumer Rupee of Rose and Marigold in Channel – 1.

• *Channel -1 (PRODUCER/FARMER – CONSUMER)*

Table 3 Market Margin

Sr. No	Particulars	Rose	Marigold
		Value in Rs./Kg	Value in Rs./Kg
1.	Produce sale price to Consumer	120	95
A	Marketing cost incurred by producer		
i.	Packaging cost	4	3
ii.	Weighing charge	1	1
iii.	Labour Cost	3	3
iv.	Miscellaneous charges	5	4
A	Total Marketing Cost	12	11
	Net price received by producer	108	84
B	Margin of the producer	40	32
C	Marketing efficiency	2.30%	2.20%
D	Price Spread	12	11
E	Producer’s Share in Consumer Rupees	89.65%	87.64%

➤ *Table 3:*

Above table reveals that the marketing price of rose and marigold through channel 1 is Rs.120, Rs.95. The cost incurred by producer in marketing of rose and marigold through channel 1 is Rs 12, Rs 11. Net price received by producer of rose and marigold is Rs 108, Rs.84. the profit margin of Producer seen in marketing of rose and marigold through channel 1 Rs 40, Rs.32. eventually the marketing efficiency seen in channel 1 is 2.30%, 2.20%, price spread seen in channel 1 is Rs 12, Rs 11 and producer's share in consumer rupee is 89.65%, 87.64%.

➤ *Table 4:*

Market margin, Marketing cost, Marketing efficiency, Price spread and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupee of Rose and Marigold in Channel – 2.

• *CHANNEL – 2 (PRODUCER/FARMER-RETAILER-CONSUMER)*

Table 4 Market Margin

S. No	Particulars	Rose	Marigold
		Value in Rs. / Kg	Value in Rs. / kg
1.	Producer sale price to retailer	116	89
2.	Cost incurred by the producer		
i.	Packaging cost	4	3
ii.	Weighing charge	1	1
iii.	Labour Cost	3	3
iv.	Miscellaneous charges	5	4
	Total Marketing Cost	12	11
3	Margin of Producer	36	26
4	Net price received by producer	104	78
5	Retailer sale price to Consumer	128	98
6	Margin of Retailer	12	9
A	Total Marketing cost	12	11
B	Total Market margin	48	35
C	Marketing Efficiency	2.13%	2.13%
D	Price Spread	24	20
E	Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees	81.25%	79.59%

➤ *Table 4:*

This table reveals that the marketing price of the rose and marigold in channel – 1, supplied by the producer/ farmer was Rs. 120/kg, Rs.95/kg, with the marketing cost incurred by the producer/farmer is Rs.12 and Rs. 11 respectively. The market margin of producer/farmer in marketing of rose and marigold is Rs.36, Rs.26 respectively. The price spread that can be seen in marketing of rose and marigold through channel-1 is Rs.24, Rs.20 respectively. The producer's share in consumer rupee in marketing of rose and marigold through channel 1 is 81.25% , 79.59% in Prayagraj district of Uttar Pradesh respectively.

➤ *Table 5:*

Market margin, Marketing cost, Marketing efficiency, Price spread and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupee of Rose and Marigold in Channel – 3.

• *CHANNEL-3 (PRODUCER/FARMER-WHOLESALE-RETAILER-CONSUMER)*

Table 5 Market Margin

S. No	Particulars	Rose	Marigold
		Value in Rs. / Kg	Value in Rs. / Kg
1.	Producer sale price to Wholesaler	116	89
a	Marketing cost incurred by producer	12	11
2	Net price received by Producer	104	78
3	Margin of Producer	36	26
4	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler		
i	Packing cost	2	2
ii	Transportation	2	1.50
iii	Miscellaneous charges	1	1
5	Total cost (i-iii)	5	4.50
6	Wholesaler price to Retailer	127	98

	Margin of wholesaler	11	9
	Marketing Cost incurred by retailer		
i.	Transportation cost	2	1
ii.	Packing cost	1	2
iii.	Miscellaneous charges	1	1
	Total Marketing Charges (i-iii)	4	4
8	Retailer price to Consumer	133	103
9	Margin of Retailer	6	5
A	Total Marketing cost	21	19.5
B	Total Market margin	53	40
C	Marketing efficiency	1.79%	1.73%
D	Price Spread	29	25
E	Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees	78.19%	75.72%

Above tables reveals that the marketing price of the rose and marigold channel -III, supplied by the producer was Rs.116, Rs.89 and the net price received by producer of rose and marigold Rs.104, Rs 78. Meanwhile, the cost incurred by the producer in marketing of rose and marigold is Rs. 12, Rs.11 and Rs. 36, Rs.26 as profit per kg of rose and marigold. The marketing cost incurred by wholesaler in marketing of rose and marigold through channel – 3 is Rs.5 , Rs.4.50. Finally, the selling price of rose and marigold per kg to the retailer is Rs.127, Rs.98. The selling price of rose and marigold from retailer to consumer is Rs133/kg, Rs.103/kg. Eventually, the price spread was seen in marketing of rose and marigold through channel-3 is Rs.29, Rs.25 , the total marketing cost in rose and marigold through channel 3 is Rs.21, Rs.19.5, the marketing efficiency in marketing of rose and marigold through channel -3 is 1.79%, 1.73% and lastly the producer's share in consumer rupee seen in marketing of rose and marigold through channel 3 is 78.19%, 75.72%. respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

It may be concluded from the study that there is an immense scope for expansion of area and production of rose and marigold in Chaka as well as in other suitable part of Prayagraj district. The cost of cultivation of rose and marigold is higher but due to good demand in market, the return are also very good. Producers can get a net profit on marketing of rose and marigold through channel-1 is Rs.40 and Rs.32, channel -2 and channel 3 Rs.36 , Rs. 26 respectively.

The study pertains to the marketing of rose and marigold in Prayagraj district of Uttar Pradesh with the main objective of prevails in studying of preferred marketing channel in marketing of rose and marigold and evaluation of marketing cost , market margin, marketing efficiency, price spread and producer's share in consumer rupee in marketing of rose and marigold. rose and marigold is majorly considered as an export oriented crop with major people using it for decorations and garland making, most of the respondents were marketing rose and marigold through channel 3 and the price spread is greater in channel 3 as compared to channel I respectively.

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